

The Coupling Constants Series and The Graviton Illusion - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series, and in particular the coupling terms describing Gravitons, it is possible to prove that there could infinite classes of distinct Gravitons. That is because Gravitons are a combination of three net curvatures. Because of this idea, any three net curvature will produce a Graviton that is unique.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

. We have analyzed the term of Graviton as a combination of three net curvature that could be either distinct or identical. That is by the spin two trait. That spin two trait, in net curvature representation means that gravity is short ranged, as the three net curvature and the invariant three sums to be a positive number.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} = \left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$[2N_{gravity} + 2] \rightarrow [2N_{gravity}] \quad (2.3)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T thesis fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. Since nature does not impose a restriction on the kind of particles to which are describing the term (2.2) and (2.3), it is possible to predict that there are infinite classes of Gravitons of distinct magnitudes. Alternatively, that if we take an even sum or certain sort, add a generator and three net curvature of certain magnitude, which belong to the prime ring, that combination will result a "Graviton like" particle.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3}$$

$$[N_{VK1}, N_{VK2}, N_{VK3}] \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$K1 \dots KN \in \mathbb{R}$$

Since spin two vanishes due to being an even number, the difference between each Graviton is the term that does not vanish in spin representation - $(2N_0)$. The smaller this term the stronger the Graviton should be. Therefore, if one analysis is correct, Gravitons classes are infinite in kind, and they are, in contrast to the first three interactions that are in a sense independent, is not independent and depends upon the composite elements. As previously mentioned, Gravitons are a superposition of net curvatures (equivalent or distinct is currently not known), which means that in order to sustain Graviton on quantum scale, it requires aligning three net curvatures in time and position. If one of the net curvature terms is not there, we no longer have the Graviton. The main point of this paper is to make a prediction about the nature of Graviton, and here it is the prediction:

(1) Gravitons are infinite in kind.

It is a daring statement to make given the fact that we did not detect even a single graviton to date, but the 8T is a daring theory. It also provides us a practical way to test whether Graviton like particles can be created in an artificial way. For example, for the electromagnetic coupling, we need the term in (2.4) to create a "Graviton like" particle, the Graviton is a matter of illusion, and it is everywhere and nowhere at the same time, as it is quite rare to create the term in (2.4) as far as one can see.

$$[(2N_{(2)}) + (e)] + \gamma + \gamma + \gamma \quad (2.4)$$

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)